

Scientific and the Oretical Characteristics of the Influence of Popular Laughter on the Development of a Work of Art

Sharipova Nilufar Shakhrillo qizi

Teacher of the Department of Russian Language and Literature of the Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: *The article analyzes the structural and semantic constructions used in Russian stories to describe smiles and laughter. Writers reproduce each type of facial reactions in their stories, using analytical or descriptive constructions depending on the artistic task.*

Key words: *humor, comedian, satire, distributors, facial expressions, smile, laughter, guffaw, grin, smirk.*

Introduction.

The humorous effect in a work of art is created by some details, a portrait of the characters, their speech. For example, in the fairy tale by L. S. Petrushevskaya "Two Sisters", the main characters - intelligent grandmothers-girls - deliberately use slang in their speech so that adults cannot expose them. The discrepancy between age and speech creates a comic effect.

Unlike other types of comedy, humor is not characterized by "superior laughter". The author likes the object of laughter, he seems to "enter the situation", and treats certain human weaknesses with understanding.

Humor most often takes the form of funny and good-natured laughter. The author, laughing at someone, can also laugh at himself. Humor reconciles a person with the imperfection of the world.

Humor as a form of comedy appeared already in the period of Antiquity, in the times of Ancient Greece, when the dramatic genre of comedy developed. The founder of ancient Greek comedy was Aristophanes, who created "Lysistrata" and "Peace". Humor then developed in the ancient Roman theater, where ancient Greek plots and characters were preserved.

Discussion and results.

As a rule, satire is especially relevant in the historical period in which the work is created. After some time, the reader may not grasp the satirical ideas, because the era described with its acute social problems is far from him. But the more universal and ineradicable the problems ridiculed by the author, the more viable the satire. Unlike direct criticism, an important component of satire is laughter, which helps to see the discrepancy between appearance and essence, form and content.

The main task of satire is to "revive" positive human qualities: kindness, truth, beauty – through ridicule of vices, stupidity, vulgarity. In order for satire to achieve its goal, it is necessary, in the words of M. E. Saltykov-Shchedrin, "firstly, that it should give the reader a sense of the ideal from which its creator sets out, and, secondly, that it should be quite clearly aware of the object against which its sting is directed."

Smile and laughter, as scientists note, are the most expressive facial reactions of a person. They accompany us throughout almost our entire life. It is generally accepted that smile and laughter are an expression of positive feelings and emotions. Most researchers note that a smile contains in its meaning

the component I feel something good now [1, p. 78]. But in real life, these phenomena can express a fairly wide range of emotions, not only positive ones. It is possible to define laughter only by starting from its opposite. First of all, it should be noted that both laughter and fear are a reaction to some problem. With fear, the problem seems insoluble, at least at this point in time. The hopelessness of the situation is emphasized by the degree of threat. Laughter, in turn, can be described "from the opposite", as an understanding of how to solve this problem and find a way out of the situation.

Laughter is based not simply on the subject's knowledge of the contradictory nature of the situation or a fixed set of logical inconsistencies in the object: laughter is an expression not of knowledge, but of understanding. Such traditional characteristics of understanding as integrity, heuristics, creativity, dialogicity, emotional-sensory, evaluative and socio-cultural conditioning, etc. fully correspond to the manifestations of the funny; at the same time, most of the conditions of laughter are private conclusions from the basic hermeneutic characteristics.

Shevyrev considers two types of laughter [2]. Farcical laughter is empty, funny, quickly fading, transient and cold inside; deep laughter, hiding tears, always having a truly important meaning, laughter that cleanses a person from everything unreasonable in favor of the reasonable. One of the sure means of distinguishing farcical laughter from comedy laughter is time, which gives its assessment to the work. A farce that has made people laugh for several weeks or months no longer makes people laugh and passes, whereas a truly artistic comedy contains laughter that lives forever. The comedies of Aristophanes, which are connected with the Greek people by their living conditions alone and which are completely alien to us in this respect, remain funny, as funny as any human folly, no matter in what nation it occurs. This is how Moliere's comedies work and the comedies of any true artist will work, notes Shevyryov.

In his study of the theory of the comic, Shevyryov turns to Aristotle's definition of the funny in *Poetics*: "Comedy, as we have said, is a reproduction of the worst people, but not in all their depravity, but in a funny form. The funny is a part of the ugly. The funny is some kind of mistake or deformity that does not cause suffering or harm, like, for example, a comic mask. It is something ugly and deformed, but without suffering" [3, p. 53]. Shevyryov expresses this more descriptively and concisely; "Aristotle in his *Poetics*, speaking of comedy, gave the following definition of the funny. "Comedy," he says, "is a representation of something base, but not always vicious, but of that shameful thing which produces the funny, for the funny is some kind of mistake, something shameful, but harmless. "For example, a funny face will be bad, distorted, but without harm" [4, No. 1, p. 108].

In his study of the theory of the comic, Shevyrev refers to Aristotle's definition of the funny in *Poetics*: "Comedy, as we have said, is the reproduction of the worst people, but not in all their depravity, but in a funny form. The funny is a part of the ugly. The funny is some kind of mistake or deformity that does not cause suffering or harm, like, for example, a comic mask. It is something ugly and deformed, but without suffering" [3, p. 53].

Repeating the well-known truth that positive heroes fade and lose their artistic persuasiveness in front of comic heroes, Shevyryov turns to the ancient heritage. "Starodum himself, so successfully compared in Prince Vyazemsky with the chorus of ancient tragedy, or with the parabasis of Aristophanes' comedy, in which the leader of the chorus addressed the audience on behalf of the author – Starodum himself, more animated than other characters, is not saved from the temptations of this impatience, which is quite natural in the audience. The element of comedy is laughter at human stupidity" [3, p. 382]. Griboyedov understood this – and avoided the shortcoming. Chatsky is far from the ideal of perfection. At first he makes too many sacrifices for society, and "then he attacks it too harshly" [3, p. 383].

No less relevant is the normative aspect of laughter as one of the regulators of value attitudes. In this aspect, laughter acquires moral and cultural significance as a mechanism for aggravating and subsequently resolving the contradictions of what is and what should be. It is also valuable for the current

stage of development of society in Russia that laughter communication affirms universal human values of freedom, filled with the meanings of purification, rebirth, unity, optimism and opposing authoritarian dogmas.

Thus, laughter as an interdisciplinary communicative phenomenon that permeates the spheres of public life acquires a universal ideological character. Such a position makes it one of the valuable testimonies of the history of mankind as the development and interaction of cultures, an important phenomenon that contributes to the understanding of social processes of the present, and a value-regulatory phenomenon that outlines the contours of the future. As a result, it is important to consider laughter as a holistic socio-cultural phenomenon, through the dynamics and logic of the existence of which social relations and cultural dynamics, traditions, norms, and values of man and humanity are comprehensively manifested.

Conclusion.

Theories of laughter are based on three key traditions. Most of the concepts are based on ideas that arose in ancient thought. The views of Plato, Aristotle, Cicero, Quintilian, who identified the axiological, aesthetic, and ethical parameters of laughter, had a decisive influence on the theory. This tradition sees the essence of the comic in a “painless mistake,” “imaginary,” “imaginary,” and “tragic,” while limiting its scope to socio-political and ethical norms [5]. Some statements about the essence and role of laughter, in demand by later theories, can also be found in Democritus, Aristophanes, and Lucian, who interpreted laughter as a necessary correlate that complements a serious view of the world. In the spirit of ancient traditions of comic liberty, laughter in their interpretation exposes the imperfection of the world and social structure to public view, calling for a change in the latter [6].

Smile and laughter in the prose of A.P. Chekhov, as in life, are a complex phenomenon with a thousand faces, each of which is unique. With the help of words, the author masterfully reproduces each type of facial reactions, resorting to analytical or descriptive constructions depending on the artistic task. Thanks to the diversity of linguistic constructions, each specific smile finds its embodiment in language.

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